

INTANGIBLE CULTURAL HERITAGE: A FUTURE PROSPECT OF HERITAGE TOURISM

Dr. Ameerza Zarrin* & Farha**

* Assistant Professor, Department of Museology, Aligarh Muslim University,
Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh

** Research Scholar, Department of Museology, Aligarh Muslim University, Aligarh, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:

Intangible cultural heritage represents the traditions or living expressions taken from ancestors and passed on to future generations such as oral traditions, performing arts, social practices, rituals, festivals, knowledge and practices related to nature or the knowledge and art to manufacture traditional crafts. Tourist visits different places to learn and experience the unique culture of India including Buddhist chanting of Laddakh, Patachitra of West Bengal, Mudiyyettu of Kerela, Kumbh mela, Kalbelia folk songs, and dances of Rajasthan and so on. Tourists exploring the cultural heritage of India offer a wonderful lifetime experience to familiarize themselves with all customs. Doing tribal photography in India gives them great joy. The richness that intangible heritage offers is one of the key motivations for travel for tourists who wish to interact with new cultures and experience the diversity of the performing arts, crafts, rituals, festive events and cuisines. Thus, cultural heritage tourism creates a powerful impetus for safeguarding and enhancement of intangible cultural heritage, as the resources it generates can be redirected to communities of tradition bearers for their sustainable development. Safeguarding intangible cultural heritage is a valuable economic source generated by cultural heritage tourism in the form of an inflow of foreign currencies. Cultural cooperation is fostered by heritage tourism, which promotes discussion, builds understanding and encourages peace and tolerance worldwide. It is clear that intangible cultural heritage builds bridges between the past, present and future, it also encourages a sense of identity and responsibility.

Key Words: Intangible Cultural Heritage, Tourism, Safeguarding, Sustainable Development

Introduction:

India is a huge country with a long history and rich culture. It has almost 5,000 years of civilized life, making it one of the world's major civilizations. Every region of India is known for its uniqueness, especially when we talk about rituals and culture. People differ in their eating habits, clothing, language and traditions, and yet are bonded together. India has always been famous for its ancient culture and rich heritage. Its tourist-friendly traditions, colorful fairs and festivals as well as diverse lifestyles and cultural heritage, are the center of attraction for tourists. The other attractions include mountain peaks, snow and river for adventure tourism; wild life and forests, beautiful beaches and landscapes for eco-tourism; pilgrimage centers for religious tourism; technological parks and science museums for science tourism. Natural wellness centers, Ayurveda, Yoga and hill stations also attract tourists. Indian handicrafts especially, jewelry, carpets, brass, bone, ivory work and leather-based goods are the main attractions of foreign tourists.

Tourists visiting India must have a deep cultural impact in their broadest sense; all tourism in India involves at least one aspect of cultural tourism. India has had many rulers over the centuries and all have influenced Indian culture. The influence of many different cultures can be seen in music, dance, architecture, festivals, language, food and traditional customs. It is because of the influence of all these different cultures that India's heritage and culture are comprehensive and vibrant. This cultural richness greatly contributes to making India a top cultural tourism destination.

Culture and heritage are important resources for tourism development, and in turn, tourism makes an important contribution to cultural development and all the domains of intangible cultural heritage play an important role in heritage tourism. According to World Trade Organization (WTO), 37% of international tourism is culturally motivated, and demand is estimated to be growing at 15% annually (Canadian Tourism Commission, 1997). Tourism has the potential to safeguard and enhance heritage and culture by bringing in revenue for historical sites, ruins and mausoleums. The special importance of the tourism industry in India is its contribution to national integration and preservation of the natural and cultural environment and the enrichment of the socio-cultural life of the people, such as preserving monuments and heritage properties and contributing to the survival of arts, crafts and cultural forms.

Tourism contributes to the preservation of various historical monuments by listing them as heritage sites. Likewise, tourism can make a substantial contribution to environment protection, biodiversity conservation and restoration, and natural resource sustainability. Because of their beauty, natural regions and pristine sites are recognized as valuable and the urge to preserve them might lead to the establishment of wildlife parks and national parks.

The great strides in the development of cultural tourism in India in recent years are one of the major

factors behind the rapid rise of India's tourism sector. Realizing its importance, the Indian government has given much emphasis to cultural tourism. The Incredible India!' campaign which led the promotional efforts of the Ministry of Tourism, has spurred the growth of Indian cultural tourism.

What is Intangible Cultural Heritage?

Intangible cultural heritage is passed on from generation to generation and is continuously recreated by groups in response to their environment, their interactions with nature and their history, giving them a way of identity and continuity, as described in the 2003 Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage. There are many things that we consider important to preserve for new generations.

They may be important due to their current or future economic value, but also because they evoke a specific emotion within us, or because they make us feel like we belong to something such as – a country, a tradition, a lifestyle. These can be objects that can be kept and buildings that can be explored, or stories that can be told and songs that can be sung. Whatever shape they take, these items form a part of a heritage, and our active efforts are needed to protect this heritage.

Like culture in general, intangible heritage is continually changing and evolving and is enriched with each new generation. Many of the expressions and manifestations of intangible cultural heritage are under threat, endangered by globalization and cultural homogenization, as well as by a lack of support, understanding and appreciation.

If intangible cultural heritage is not preserved, it risks being lost for all time or frozen as a bygone tradition. Preservation of this heritage and transmission of it to future generations makes it stronger and keeps it alive while allowing it to transform and adapt. There is a risk that some elements of intangible cultural heritage may perish or fade without assistance, but how can we safeguard and manage a heritage which is continuously changing and an element of 'living culture' without freezing or trivializing it? (UNESCO, Intangible Cultural Heritage). There are the following five domains of Intangible cultural heritage;

- Oral traditions and expressions, including language as a vehicle of intangible cultural heritage
- Performing arts
- Social practices, rituals and festive events
- Knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe
- Traditional craftsmanship.

Oral Tradition & Expressions Including Language as a Vehicle of Intangible Cultural Heritage:

Oral communication is a long-standing tradition in India which includes chants, myths, epic songs and poems, legends, tales, prayers, and other elements that are orally transmitted from generation to generation. Language itself provides extensive information about the community's culture and tradition. Some popular modes of oral communication may include travelers' stories, daily group prayer gatherings in towns and villages, fairs and festivals and religious conclaves organised on a frequent basis at major pilgrimage destinations such as Kumbh Mela at Allahabad. Regular prayer gatherings of Gandhiji are a good illustration of how his message was spread by word of mouth. Oral tradition may be described as the recording, preservation, and interpretation of historical knowledge, or the narration of events based on personal experiences, or it can be an oral singing, chanting offered in rituals, or narration of a story related to a certain community. Folklore, songs, tales, and stories that have been passed down through the generations via word of mouth also belong to the category of oral tradition.

When a society lacks written language or has limited access to writing instruments, oral traditions face the challenge of proper transmission and verifiability of the accurate version. Due to the growth of cities and industries in many countries, the opportunities to remember and transfer our folk practices, songs and narratives have faded away and are not in living form as the opportunities to remember and transfer them have been lost. But in India, the rural society is still large and a large section of the community lives in villages which makes the oral tradition in living form. Mantras, hymns, sankirtans in temples, folk songs, legends, cult practices, Rasleela tradition, harvest songs and rituals, songs and legends associated with the festive events, Nautanki, Ramayana Katha and other tales, Harikatha, Vedic Yajna, recitation of Quran, Bible or Guru Granth and other such scriptures are practiced a lot. All these holy books available in written version today were once in oral versions before they were written. Oral traditions reflect our diverse society and are important in transmitting age-old wisdom and social norms which attracts many visitors to India to study the culture.

Vedic Chanting © Sangeet Natak Akademi, New Delhi, India

The most crucial aspect of safeguarding oral traditions and expressions is ensuring that they continue to have a role in society. It is also necessary that opportunities for transmission of knowledge from person to person survive, such as opportunities for tourists to connect with practitioners and pass on stories. Oral tradition generally forms a part of festivities and cultural celebrations, so there is a need to promote these events and new contexts such as storytelling festivals, and encouragement to allow traditional creativity to find new ways of expression in order to attract more tourists. There are lots of possibilities for the tourist to recognize and take part in those occasions, in which the oral traditions play a significant role. Unique expressive features, along with intonation and a large number of changing styles, can now be recorded as audio or video, as well as non-verbal story components including gestures and mimicry among performers and tourists. Mass media and communication technologies may be used to preserve and reinforce oral traditions and expressions through broadcasting recorded performances each to their communities of origin and a much wider audience.

Performing Arts:

The performing arts, an innate form of Indian culture and heritage, have been celebrated in the country for thousands of years including our cultural expressions like dance, music and theatre. All forms of performing arts in India, including music, dance and theatre, are known for their uniqueness and symbolize the rich culture and traditions of ancient times. These are considered good practices as they have improved management and attractiveness through the years to attract more tourists.

The dances of India are as old as the Indus Valley Civilization which are recorded on carved stones that the historical Indian civilization gave prominence to various dance forms. These different dance forms in India offer scintillating experiences to the viewers. Indian tradition is rich in showcasing a number of classical and folk dances. Each state of India has its folk dance, which shows that the diversity in culture and tradition is also reflected in the diversity of Indian folk dances. Folk dances are done to celebrate the arrival of seasons, births, marriage, and festivals, among other things. Some famous classical dance forms are Kathakali, Bharatnatyam, Koodiyattom, Kuchipudi, Mohiniyattom and Odissi. Dance and music have always happened to be the most popular choice of tourists as Indian dances are very popular around the world. It is not surprising that many tourists – Indian and foreigners visit dance festivals. Some of the very popular dance and music festivals are the Khajuraho dance festival of Madhya Pradesh, the Konark dance festival of Orissa, and the Chennai Dance and music festival. The workshops on folk dances that are organized nowadays by a number of state tourism boards (for example, the Chhau dance workshop organized by the West Bengal Tourism Development Corporation on the World Tourism Day 2014 at the Victoria Memorial hall) are the most effective culture immersion options available to tourists. In India, without the performance of a folk dance stay at a heritage hotel or a visit to a theme village-like Chowki Dhani in Jaipur, Rajasthan is incomplete. Kalbelia dance and the fire dance accompanied by music by local Manganiyar musicians are the main attraction of the desert safaris of Rajasthan.

Kalbelia Dance, Rajasthan © Swan Tours

The true rhythm of India can be found in its folk music, which is the music of the masses. There is a song for everything in India. It is like having a background music score for every possible scene of life. Various aspects of Indian folk music elements attract tourists of special interest such as artists, cultural tourists and musicians from all over the world. The Rajasthan International Folk Festival witnesses an exciting fusion of international and Indian folk music which held annually in Mehrangarh Fort in the royal city of Jodhpur, attracting thousands of patrons from India and the rest of the world. Tansen Music Festival, Gwalior is one of the famous tourist attractions especially dedicated to the pillar of Indian classical music, the great musician Tansen. Visitors from all over the world come here to watch the live performance of musicians. In Natyanjali Dance Festival which is organized with the support of the Ministry of Tourism – Government of India, Department of Tourism – Government of Tamil Nadu and Natyanjali Trust – Chidambaram, prominent dancers from all over India perform and congregate at the temple to pay homage to Lord Nataraja. Dover Lane Music Festival is held every year for the local folks and tourists in Kolkata. Many musicians participate in this festival to add more fun and enjoyment to the visitors. The fete also comes with dance, music and art. This event makes a proper contribution to the preservation of music and art among the deserving artists. Tourists from all over the world visit here to witness the mesmerizing performances of talented musicians. Music tourism is not just about music; it's really about selling an experience in general, where people travel to a city, country or town from all over the world to attend a music festival or music show without any reluctance. The indulgence of travelers and young people has fueled this industry. These music festivals welcome musicians and singers from all over the world, not only famous artists but also amateurs have the opportunity to establish themselves and showcase their talents. Music tourism is not limited to this only. It also helps to create local employment and gives cities the opportunity to showcase their culture, ethos and heritage.

Dover Lane Music Conference, Kolkata Photo © Koushikvocal

The colorful diversity of Indian folk culture is best represented by the unique art of folk theatre which reaches out to various segments of the Indian population. Today, many socio-cultural organizations are playing an important role in reviving, propagating and appreciating Indian folk theatre by organizing workshops, seminars, fairs and festivals, thereby promoting India's cultural heritage and tourism prospects on the world map. A folk drama is enjoyed by people not because of its production value but because of its transmission and the relationship between the audience and the performer. The informal mode of presentation, the simplicity and freedom from all boredom of technicalities is the life of a folk theatre. Traditional folk drama in India has deep roots in society, just because it strictly follows the tradition. Examples of famous Indian folk theatre include Jatra from West Bengal, Yakshagana from Karnataka, Naqal from Punjab, Bhavai and Akhyana from Gujarat, Kalaripayattu – a martial dance drama and Theyyam from Kerala, Swang from Harayana, Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan and Malwa regions of Madhya Pradesh, Bhand Pather from Kashmir, Ramleela during the Dussehra festival from all over Northern India, Terukkuttu – a Tamil street theatre, Tamasha from Maharashtra, etc. Puppetry is also a very important form of folk theatre in India which is famous in the states of India such as Rajasthan, Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, and Karnataka. Bharat Kala Museum in Udaipur, Rajasthan hosts daily puppet shows for tourists. A short visit to a local fair together with witnessing Ramleela is a type of offering that features nowadays on Diwali itineraries of the many accommodation establishments in India. There are many other types of traditional semi-dramatic communication media such as Nahan, Bahurupia art, the mask procession, etc. The Bahurupia, for instance, is one of the foremost ancient forms of entertainment prevalent in most parts of India. They are most witty people, skilled at mimicry imitation and costuming. They reside in one place for days together and perform jhankis and monodramas of various types various kinds in front of their patrons.

Ramlila, Folk Theatre, North India Photo © Hari Mahidhar / Dinodia Photo Library

Social Practices, Rituals and Festive Events:

From ancient times, people have always held festivals or ceremonies according to their culture to express their happiness, sorrow, and joy. In India, the best way to escape everyday life and discover the true beauty of India lies in its cultural heritage, spirituality and interesting folktales. Festivals and rituals are both components and products of a community. This is one of the most diverse and active ICH categories which covers the secular and religious, every day and extraordinary. Such heritage can often be bundled into a single tourism product. However, it remains a challenge to safeguard values associated with rituals and sacred practices when developing tourism products for emerging destinations.

India's festivals have always piqued the interest of tourists from all over the world as they allow them to harmoniously blend in with the cultural variety and discover a fascinating side of the country that leaves them fascinated and inspired. Festivals are key figures in the development and promotion plans of several destinations. They have a universal significance in social and cultural activities, and they have been developed and designed as tourist attractions because they provide opportunities for the local people to share culture, experience and knowledge. They help tourists to observe how a country celebrates its holidays and carry on its customs and traditions. Although festivals seem to be organized with the sole purpose of promoting the culture of the destinations and attracting tourists, they are essentially important to ensure the continuity of the culture and traditions of the local people. Festivals are widely used by the tourism industry as cultural packages. This process can be observed on a much smaller level in many different states. Every state has its festival for example Gujarat fest, Bengal fest, Rajasthan fest etc. which are generally celebrated during the major festival season of the region. The Chaitra Parva Chhau festival in Orissa is one of the popular cultural tours in India and is celebrated by the 'Bhuiyans Tribe' in many regions. Elephanta Festival is the most famous fete of Mumbai which is organized under the support of the Maharashtra Tourism Development Corporation (MTDC), to showcase and promote the classic culture of Maharashtra via music and dance performances by artists. During the Pachmarhi Festival, many cultural programs such as art performances, exhibition and craft fair are organized that brings great excitement among tourists and local folks. It also brings amazing Indian Folk Arts displays to enrapture the audience. To make the day overwhelming, cultural evenings are also arranged every day in which various artists around the world participate. There is a majority of programs which plays an effective role in preserving the rich cultural heritage of India. There are several stalls arranged to exhibit and sell products from sponsored artisans of Handloom and Handicrafts Development Corporation. To showcase Orissa's rich history, culture and traditions, Shreekshetra Utsav (Puri Festival) is organized each year to familiarize tourists with various aspects of the festival such as Shree Jayadeva Odissi Sangeet Samaroh, Handicrafts Expo, Shrimad Bhagabata Parayana, Odissi Food Festival, Sand Art Exhibition and Handloom Expo. The main part of this Utsav is Shree Jayadeva Odissi Sangeet Samaroh which is organized in association with the District Administration – Puri, Government of Orissa, Department of Tourism and Culture and also the Orissa Sangeet Natak Academy. The most entertaining part of this festival is its Odissi dance, music and appetizing cuisines which help to promote Orissa's cultural heritage and its own culture. To grab the attention of tourists, puppet shows are organized during the folk festival which defines scenes from Indian epics like Ramayana, Mahabharat, etc. This type of fest showcases a number of the traditional culture of the respective region like music, costume, craft, dance and food etc.

Makar Sankranti also known as Lohri, Bihu, Uttarayana, Pongal, and Khichdi marks an astronomical phenomenon at its origin. It is an ancient festival that is still celebrated across the country on 13-14 January. Festivals come in a variety of forms-

- Modern fest

- Festivals of harvests
- Festivals of livestock
- Gods/ Goddesses celebrations
- Saints/Legendary Heroes festivals
- State/national festivals
- Festivals of seasons

The majority of these categories, however, overlap and are adaptable, so a single event might be seasonal, agricultural, and religious at the same time. Our most popular festivities are drawn from old agrarian and astronomical rituals, such as Baisakhi (Punjab spring festival), the Bohag Bihu (Assamese spring festival), and others, which are held between mid-April and mid-May. Both of these festivals have a strong agricultural theme. Goa Carnival is a time of entertainment and fun for tourists from all over the world. Many visitors, regardless of their nationality and social status, participate in this exhilarating festival. Festivals help to attract tourists to an area, sell local products, increase employment, preserve and develop infrastructure, safeguard intangible cultural heritage, and maintain peace.

Teej Festival © Tour My India Pvt.

Goa Carnival © India Tours

Rituals are repetitive and highly symbolic. Every society has its rituals. These can relate to specific performances by an individual or a group of people. The location of performances can be one's own house or public places like riverbanks, wells, hills, fields and reservoirs. It may involve only a particular community or may provide an opportunity for exchange between several groups living in different hierarchies. Over time, ritual practices have been linked to specific religions. The Hindu samskaras, the Christian ceremonies of christening, baptism, and confirmation, the Jewish Shabbat, commemoration of the Azadari by Muslims during Muharram etc. are also rituals. Special fire rituals were practiced by every householder in the Vedic period. Some of the different categories of rituals are as follows;

- Birth Rituals
- Rituals to Appease Gods
- Rituals of Fertility
- Initiation Rites
- Grief Rituals

Rituals deeply affect people's individual and collective lives. They serve to reaffirm one's allegiance to a specific social order. There are rituals at every stage of our life. From birth to death, from sunrise to sunset, from summer to winter, rituals are the milestones which decide our existence. Rituals are more than just performances, they also serve to make and confirm our identity.

Baptism Muharram © Navin Creations

Procession (Image: PTI)

Knowledge and Practices Concerning Nature and the Universe:

This category includes beliefs about the workings of the physical universe, land use, traditional agricultural practices, and maintaining harmony with nature. The cultural center and walking trails invite tourists to learn about Indian culture and beliefs about their land and its custodianship. The overwhelming stress in the workplace and the hustle and bustle of life in big crowded cities causes people to run to unfamiliar places and relax. These are usually weekend trips to nearby quiet resorts or long road trips in a natural environment to find peace. Due to low treatment costs, quality healthcare infrastructure and availability of highly qualified doctors, India has been ranked in the top three medical tourism destinations in Asia after Thailand and Singapore. There are many tourists who are traveling from far away to India for alternative treatment as well. Traditional medicine in India may be classified into codified (Siddha, Unani, Ayurveda, Homeopathy) and non-codified (folk medicine) systems.

The 'folk medicines' are evolved from traditional practices and beliefs from centuries of trial and error experiences that have been passed on orally to the practitioners and their knowledge is jealously guarded. The domestic "Daadi Maa Ke Nuskhe", as well as the preparations of remarkably high curative value by the hakims and vaidas – India's unlicensed but not unskilled faith healers could be examples of folk medicines. Whether in the forests of Madhya Pradesh, Chhattisgarh, Himalayas, Andhra Pradesh, or Car Nicobar, Indian wildlife is home to a plethora of medicinal plants from which a variety of folk medicines are prepared. Panchvati in Nasik, Sakshi Ganapati in Srisailam, Kapildhara in Amarkantak, Manali in Himachal Pradesh etc. are some important sites in India where folk healers can be found.

India is also known for its traditional medicinal system for instance – Ayurveda- knowledge of life, which is an ancient healing system. This system originated in India and developed between 2500-500BC it combines naturopathy with various natural therapies that work as a vitality booster. Yoga classes are added to these therapies. The practice has a dual purpose: To maintain a healthy person's health, rejuvenate, purify and prevent disease and cure the patient's illness. Ayurveda has played an important role in modern times as people all over the world seek to come within its protective zone. The national and international acceptance of Ayurvedic healing has certainly broadened the boundaries and possibilities of Ayurvedic tourism. They have no side effects but are very rejuvenating. All over the world, there is now more interest in this Indian traditional medicine system and these rejuvenation packages have been added to tourism marketing. Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Tamil Nadu have developed many resorts with Ayurvedic packages which are attracting worldwide attention. Likewise weekend resorts have come up, within a distance of 200-300 km around the metropolis. One can visit from Kochi to Munnar or Spice Village or neighborhoods of Mumbai places such as Mahabaleshwar, Lonawala, near Bangalore – Soukya, Jindal, near Jaipur – Mandwa or from Delhi to Ananda

Resort near Rishikesh etc.

People from across the world also come to India to practice yoga and meditation in Rishikesh, Uttaranchal which has been practiced for centuries. India is also known as “Yoga- Bhoomi” and gateway to the heavens as it has been known for its yoga, spirituality, secular nature and religious tolerance since time immemorial. In the past, yoga belonged only to yogis, but in the modern era, it is for everyone. Yoga incorporates old theories, observations, and principles about body, mind, and spirit that help to unite them. There is no wonder people all over the world are looking to the Indian subcontinent for guidance on a more spiritually satisfying lifestyle.

Ayurveda Treatment © India Mart

Tourists in Rishikesh Vinyasa Yoga School © Rishikesh Vinyasa Yoga School

Traditional Craftsmanship:

Folk crafts are the artistic expression of people's spirit in physical form, regardless of their functional and decorative ways. They are pillars of the material culture of communities and explore the complex relationship between the environment and native communities. These make up the majority of souvenirs purchased by tourists, especially in new destinations prior to the emergence of mass-produced items, which tend to be cheaper or readily available. The arts and crafts of India are famous within the world, even hold world records and are appreciated by people all over the world. India's glorious past and cultural diversity form a potent blend that draws millions of tourists to its heritage tourist attractions every year.

The roots of Indian arts and crafts are very deep and they can influence generations to come. The current status of crafts in India is greatly indebted to the rich craft traditions of the past. Around the world, traditional crafts and artefacts are the objects of curiosity for contemporary tourists. While tourism-induced consumption can create demand for the traditional craft sector, the consequences are far-reaching. The economic implications of tourism-craft linkage depend on the effectiveness of the sub-sectors of tourism such as retailing, leisure services etc., to effectively harness the locally produced crafts and artefacts into the tourism market (Saji & Narayanaswamy, 2011). The main impact of Indian arts and crafts on cultural tourism is through what we may call cultural shopping or the discriminatory purchase of examples of various kinds of work. Almost all tourists wish to buy some such souvenirs, and therefore their sale is of great importance.

The International Conference on Tourism and Handicrafts, held in Tehran from 13 to 15 May 2006, was UNWTO's first and most likely, first international conference ever held with a specific focus on the linkage between handicrafts and tourism. The tourism industry provides an important export marketplace for many crafts products. For example, hotels and restaurants require a variety of craft products to equip and furnish their installations. Craftsmanship plays a very significant role in representing the traditions and culture of any region or country. For e.g. Kashmir is famous for carving on walnut wood, embroidery on wool, carpets and

wooden boxes painted by hands for decoration and utility. The northeastern states are known for producing a wide range of beautiful bamboo and cane products and eco-friendly crafts for everyday use. Kalamkari is a block-printed or hand-painted cotton fabric which is one of the most beautiful arts and crafts of Telangana & Andhra Pradesh. A tie and dye method of fabric decoration or art is known as Bandhani which originated within the Western Part of India such as Gujarat, Rajasthan and parts of Punjab and is popular throughout India and the world. Some tribal crafts are worth mentioning here like Dhokra from west Bengal, Warli Folk Paintings from Maharashtra, Tanjore Paintings or Thanjavur Paintings from Tamil Nadu, Madhubani Art from Bihar, Saura Paintings from Odisha, Bhil Art from Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Gond from Madhya Pradesh, Pattachitra Paintings from Odhisha & West Bengal, Kalamazethu Art from Kerala and so on. Many countries, which consider crafts as the mainstay of tourism development, have established tourist facilities near the main centers of handicraft production. Some attempt to show their originality and identity by offering new products made by combining national symbols with their handicrafts. Traditional craftsmanship is one of the important contributors to the economy. Tourists from all over the world are attracted to craftsmanship and used to buy the things and even they gather knowledge from it. In this way, we can revive our culture and overall it also benefits the economy.

Tourism is the number one industry of the 21st century and handicraft is one of the fastest- growing activities which together create a logical and powerful combination. The Ministry of Tourism and Culture, Government of India assigned National Productivity Council (NPC) to conduct a survey on the spending of foreign tourists on handicrafts in India. The main motive of the survey was to find out what proportion the visiting foreign tourists spend on handicrafts (total and items-wise) during their stay in India and to develop a Crafts/Tourism Index defined as tourist per day expenditure on handicrafts) for India which is suggested by UNESCO.

Tourist buying craftwork © Jewels of Jaipur - Pat Ryan

Bone Handicraft © Jagran Prakashan Limited

Madhubani Art

Conclusion:

The perfect amalgamation of language, culture, religion, art, traditions and customs is gorgeously, reflected in India. Its natural beauty, landscapes from deserts to mountains and beaches and varied temperatures make it a must-visit country for tourists. As one of the fastest-growing and most profitable industries in the world, tourism can provide an opportunity for local communities to express pride in their own culture, thus providing the momentum to revive endangered traditions and cultural practices. It can effectively generate income and employment through the development of natural and cultural resources. Tourism allows interaction between people of different nationalities and backgrounds, thereby promoting dialogue between cultures and encouraging cultural diversity and creativity. Cities and towns are increasingly becoming popular destinations, especially for cultural tourists, and there is increasing recognition of the economic potential of tourism and culture. The uncontrolled growth of tourism can also lead to environmental degradation, destruction of fragile ecosystems and social and cultural conflicts. Tourism in India should be developed in a way that welcomes and entertains visitors in a way that does not infringe or destroy the environment, while supporting and maintaining the indigenous culture in the places where it operates. The recognition of economic potential by tourism and cultural industries grows as cities and towns are becoming increasingly popular destinations, especially for cultural tourists. The uncontrolled growth of tourism can also lead to environmental degradation, destruction of fragile ecosystems and social and cultural conflicts. Tourism in India should be developed in a way that accommodates and entertains visitors in a way that does not infringe on or destroy the environment while supporting and maintaining the indigenous culture in the places where it operates. Further, since tourism is a multi-faceted activity, and is primarily a service industry, it will be necessary that all branches of the Central and State governments, as well as the private sector and non-governmental organizations, become active participants in the effort to achieve sustainable development in tourism if India is to become a global player in the tourism sector. Improving the quality of life and generating various economic benefits, conservation of cultural heritage as a concept having environmental, economic and cultural aspects can contribute to sustainable development. The main reason for cultural diversity is Intangible cultural heritage which specifically guarantees sustainable development. In recent years, growing interest in the local way of life and festivals has promoted the conservation of intangible cultural heritage. In cultural heritage tourism government need to put on more effort into providing skilled multi Lingual guided tours. Doing so will enhance the interest of tourists who come to know in detail the culture of a place. We should discuss practical measures to develop, manage and market tourism products based on intangible cultural heritage. The guidelines should be followed by tourism policymakers and other stakeholders while recommending actions to promote tourism through the safeguarding of intangible cultural heritage. Encouragement of often struggling musicians, singers and dancers by the tourist industry would appear to serve several useful purposes the opportunity of witnessing the performances of such professional dancers and singers whom otherwise they would have much difficulty in locating. The industry focus on the "Atithi Devo Bhavah" campaign, targeting foreign tourists to the country. It is evident from the above discussion that the Intangible Cultural Heritage of India plays a vital role in heritage tourism so we need to preserve, safeguard and promote it.

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